

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EFFECTS OF AGING FACTORS ON DAMAGE IN STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY :

The increasing use of structural composites made from carbon fiber and organic matrix leads us to investigate thermo-mechanical quality and aging relationships. Multidisciplinary effects of aging factors introduce complex phenomena which can substantially alter mechanical properties of composite laminates and reduce their lifetime. After a review of aging effects, the main parameters introduced within ordinary environmental conditions subjected to thermo-structural composites are described. The combination of two parameters, temperature and oxygen diffusion, makes it extremely complex to study combined aging effects and understand corresponding mechanical results. A single surface thermo-oxidation gives rise to corrosion, surface stress state, and microcracking which are responsible for degradation of mechanical properties. Each effect can be modeled separately. This paper predicts an oxidized layer using an oxygen diffusion-reaction method. This technique is complex, however a combined study incorporating all multidisciplinary effects is significantly more so. To date, there has been no attempt to incorporate all these effects into a mechanical behavior model. As to degradation in the whole volume of the composite, it seems easier if only viscous behavior of the matrix is considered (without cracking or interface problems). For thermal aging, there exists a dynamic compromise between crosslinking and chain degradation which can be represented by a displacement of the glass transition temperature (T_g). The paper presents a multiscale mechanical approach including this T_g internal variable in order to understand the evolution of the viscoelastic behavior of composite laminates aged under various conditions.

KEYWORDS : organic matrix composites, thermal aging, thermo-oxidation, mechanical behavior, damage

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber / organic matrix composite laminates have great potential as light structural materials for long term use. Under the general term “durability” there is a combination of mechanical and chemical parameters responsible for the progressive damage of composite materials [1]. The subject is complex since it is controlled by both a wide range of aging factors as well as test time. In the laboratory, it is difficult to reproduce and manage realistic test conditions, since it is necessary to involve many parameters at the same time: loading, temperature, moisture, and radiation, for example. The mechanisms of aging associated with each of these parameters individually are so poorly understood that the link between structure and properties have not yet been established [2, 3]. In addition the accelerated artificial aging carried out in laboratories, intended to reproduce practical usage conditions, adds a further level of complexity to the problem [4]. Thus, there are such a range of interlinked parameters that analytical methods of evaluation of the long-term behavior become unreliable.

To answer questions from industrial partners concerning durability, it is necessary to consider each aspect of aging individually and then combine them to give the most accurate prediction of real

behavior. In order to identify the primary cause of aging in composite applications, it is important to know the combined effects of the other associated parameters. To achieve this it is necessary to invoke both the physics of polymers and the science of composite materials, which is a gigantic task.

Aging is a process which modifies the structure of materials. This process, generally irreversible, causes a modification in material properties with use. Depending on the conditions of degradation, the material generally shows a transformation which remains even after suppression of the cause of aging. This deterioration is caused by the effect of mechanical, chemical, thermal, radiant or electrical action on the material. In general they apply simultaneously producing a combined aging effect. These combinations make it extremely complex to study materials aged under only a single selected effect. The aim of such research is to select one cause of aging appropriate to the study while avoiding or minimizing any additional extraneous effects.

AGING FACTORS

Aging occurs by apparent degradation such as oxidation, corrosion, and cracking, as well as through invisible damage within the chemical structure such as chain cutting. Such damage are consequences of the physical and chemical aging of the composite matrix. Physical aging is that which modifies the structural organization of macromolecules in space without modifying the chemical composition of the backbone. Chemical aging is that which modifies the chemical structure of the backbone through various mechanisms such as reticulation, depolymerization, elimination and substitution. In industrial applications the effects of aging factors lead primarily to the following results:

1. Temperature induced dilation or shrinkage, giving rise within the composite to many stresses whose intensity can lead to cracking of the matrix. With oxygen in air, the composite is subjected to thermo-oxidation and its consequences. The thermo-physical aging of the thermoset networks always occurs in combination with thermo-chemical aging and the other effects due to temperature. The thermolysis effect is especially important when the temperature is next to the glass transition of the resin.
2. The state of stresses within the composite can lead to physical aging through thermal mechanisms (differential expansion between fiber and matrix) or mechanics (fatigue, creep). In any case this physical aging changes the macromolecular organization, then cracking occurs. The resultant cracking is always facilitated by a combination of environmental factors which when applied together can exacerbate their individual effects.
3. The absorption of various substances, gas or liquids, involves either a chemical modification of the matrix or a modification of its structural organization. The action of water is a good example which leads to differential swelling of each ply of the composite and even plasticization of the matrix or its hydrolysis [5].
4. The diffusion of oxygen creates a brittle oxidized layer which leads to slow degradation by corrosion of the matrix and weight loss. Thermo-oxidation can lead by itself to surface cracking of the matrix confined between fibers, but it is often enhanced by the action of thermal stresses even without additional mechanical loading.
5. X-rays, electrons, and radiation in the UV-IR range cause aging in composites through degradation of the molecular structure. In conjunction with oxygen this causes respectively radio-oxidation and photo-oxidation.

If the laboratory results are to be representative of those obtained under real aging conditions, they can be used only for comparison, without separate interpretation of each parameter brought into play. It remains the case that the mechanisms of the various aging factors can be the same ones, very different ones, or even complementary causes which accelerate degradation. This spectrum of aging factors draws into question the equivalence of the results obtained by natural and artificial accelerated methods. Heterogeneity, orthotropic character and format of the composite structures are other aspects to be taken into account when considering the effects of aging.

The problem of aging in composites is very complex. Should we be satisfied with broad studies revealing generalized properties? The current trend is to determine the mechanisms of aging by testing only one or a few selected parameters in order to better understand the long term behavior of composites. If the combined effect of temperature, oxygen and radiation work together to efficiently destroy the chemical structure of the matrix, mechanical loading acts in addition to degrade the material. A simple thermo-mechanical test carried out under an oxidizing atmosphere is difficult to interpret with the combined actions of these aging factors.

PRIMARY AGING EFFECTS

To solve the problem of aging, it is necessary to subject the composites to many rigorous tests in order to qualify and account for the behavior of these materials under normal usage conditions. This work requires development of tests able to give a response at the same time from both the perspective of mechanical resistance and that of physico-chemical degradation. However, to understand the long-term behavior of composites, it is also necessary to separate or combine the tests in order to better analyze the evolution of relevant parameters. Thus, we must study the lifetime of structural composites, used at elevated temperatures, subjected to various mechanical and thermal tests applied together or separately. A separate analysis of the damage due purely to thermal effects makes it possible to integrate fundamental physico-chemical parameters in behavior laws or lifetime models.

Excluding mechanical stresses applied to the structural composites, time and the environment are the two principal elements of aging. Time is an independent element whereas the environment includes multiple variables. To be understood as a whole, the aging generated by environmental conditions should depend on a multidisciplinary approach. Unfortunately in this case analysis of the results quickly becomes inextricable. Therefore it is better to separate and examine one or two principal aging factors relevant to the conditions for applications.

Among those already quoted above, the most important parameter of the aging factors is temperature. For organic matrix composites, only the resin is affected, as carbon fibers are inert under ordinary use conditions. If one examines the effects of just the parameter temperature, one must expect physico-chemical evolution of the matrix in the bulk of the composite material. However, in ordinary applications, thermo-structural composites generally evolve in air. In this case we are dealing with a combination of the effects of temperature and air. From the thermo-oxidizing effect of these two factors, aging will occur differently on the surface and volume of the composite. In the early days of thermal testing of aging mechanisms, it was sufficient to measure the residual mechanical properties of aged composites at various temperatures. In recent publications [2, 3] the modes of degradation remain insufficiently explained. In any rigor, to account for the elementary mechanisms of degradation, analyses of the surface and internal volume must be made on composite materials subjected to isotherms or thermal cycles of long times.

1. Surfacer aging

Combined with the temperature, the oxygen in air is a major parameter for thermo-structural applications. Surface aging is concerned with a fine oxidized layer which rarely exceeds 0,2 mm, even under severe thermo-oxidizing conditions. Within this fine damaged layer, mass-loss and microrupturing take place, and play an important role for the lifetime of composites. To form the oxidized layer, oxygen diffuses into the resin and reacts with certain components of the macromolecular structure determined by the specific kinetics [6].

When attached to the polymer structure, oxygen makes it heavier. On the other hand, oxygen, diffusional or present in the bulk, can form volatile products which when escaping reduces the polymer weight. The processes of diffusion and reaction can be formulated using a diffusion law of Fick and the kinetics of decomposition of the structure. In a composite laminate, the diffusion of oxygen occurs differently according to transverse or longitudinal directions of fibers. Using mechanistic schemes of radical decomposition considering at least 6 possible reactions between initiation and termination, it is possible to determine profiles of oxygen concentration, C , from the surface of the material and to draw the corresponding oxidized thickness [7]:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = D_i \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_i^2} - k_2 C [P^\circ] + k_6 [PO_2^\circ]^2 \quad \text{with principal directions of the composite: } i = 1, 2 \text{ or } 3.$$

D is the diffusion coefficient obtained by measurement of permeability, x is the oxidation depth and $[P^\circ]$ and $[PO_2^\circ]$ are the main radicals obtained from the radical decomposition scheme and matching the rate constants, k. If $r(C)$ is the rate of oxygen consumption of radical entities $[P^\circ]$ and $[PO_2^\circ]$, the distribution of oxidation products through the thickness of the material is:

$$Q(C) = \int r(C) dt$$

With this relation, the thickness of the oxidized layer (OLT) can be determined. Figure 1 schematically shows oxidation profiles through the thickness of the material and the thickness of the oxidized layer established according to an arbitrary criterion $[1/2 Q_s(t)]$. The boundary condition, $Q_s(t)$, considers that the break-up of oxygen entering the surface of the material is instantaneous.

Fig. 1 Oxidation profile vs samples thickness and determination of the thickness of oxidized layer (OLT) using an arbitrary criterion

Considering the steady state of aging mechanisms, progressive exposure times show that the oxidized thickness tends towards an asymptote. However, during an isotherm, the degradation of the material does not stop. A very slow development of the oxidized layer occurs by a constant thickening towards the core of the material, creating a phenomenon of almost imperceptible ablation of the surface. In addition, the profile of the oxygen concentration which leads to the progression of oxidation can also lead to a profile of weight loss that is directly comparable with the experimental thermo-gravimetric results [8, 9]. During an isothermal aging or a thermal cycling, oxidation will lead step by step to microruptures then microcracks. A possible scenario of the appearance of a crack and its progression towards the core of the material can be described over time [10]:

- at the beginning of the thermal treatment, there is instantaneous surface oxidation on contact with air. It should be noted that a post-cure after molding of the composite already involves the existence of a fine oxidized layer,
- as for any polymer, a reaction between oxygen and matrix leads to compaction of the structure. In the same way, as a general rule observed in polymers, the compactness involves a light volume variation of the reacting layer,
- the ductile part which is linked to the oxidized layer adapts to this volume variation because of its better deformation capacity. In contrast the fine fragile oxidized layer, bound on the one hand to fibers and on the other hand with the ductile part, feels a deformation constrained by this withdrawal. This situation generates a state of tensile stresses of the fragile layer,
- the stress intensity is higher where the structural modification of the polymer is largest, i.e. in the vicinity of the surface of the material,

- the particular surface morphology acquired by erosion added to the stress intensity lead together to the occurrence of multiple microruptures in the oxidized layer. Finally, the coalescence of microruptures leads to the formation of a microcrack.

The unstable propagation of the microcrack leads its end (front) in the more ductile virgin part. After each new propagation, oxygen diffuses along both faces of the microcrack which is surrounded itself by a new oxidized layer. In this way, there is a self-propagation of the microcrack by progression of the fragile oxidized layer. Generally created within the fiber/matrix interface or near the interface if the energy of interfacial cohesion is strong, a microcrack leads to a transverse or longitudinal crack of the composite [11]. Consequently, the crack density will modify the properties until rupture.

2. Volume aging

If the thermo-oxidation effect is indeed dominating for the properties at rupture, it is however only concerned with the surface layers of the material. The chemical structure in the body of the composite is also affected during the isotherm, but instead this is manifest through a modification of the viscoelastic behavior of the matrix. Under the conditions of applied temperature, physico-chemical aging produces a combination of degradation and consolidation of the structure. The thermolysis effect tends to break the polymer chains creating free radicals, themselves leading to reorganization [12]. Over long aging times thermal agitation is weak but the structure evolves nonetheless to a stable state : the entropy of configuration of the chains decreases little by little and the free volume tends towards a homogeneous distribution. In addition, local movements in the matrix of the composite can lead to particular morphologies. During thermal aging, there are elementary formation mechanisms which lead to separation of thermoset and thermoplastic phases, of which the resins are increasingly constructed [13].

One way to follow volume aging is to examine the evolution of the glass transition temperature, T_g . Although this includes effects of the oxidized surfaces, since structural parts are thick, the fine layer of surface oxidation can be neglected. Initially, the aging temperature consolidates the matrix, similar to a long post-cure. In this first stage, T_g increases. In a second stage, a combination of consolidation and degradation occurs, generally favoring the latter. In this second stage, T_g decreases. Kung *et al* gave an expression representing the evolution of T_g according to the aging temperature and time [14]. To describe the mechanisms of degradation and consolidation, it is possible to introduce a physico-chemical variable representing a reticulation density with the following mechanistic form [15]:

where Z is the result from the formation of entities X as well as the decomposition of entities Y . k_1 and k_2 are reaction rates following Arrhenius's law. The cross-linking density τ_R and the evolution of Z growing at an aging time t are respectively defined by:

$$\tau_R(t) = \frac{[Z(t)]}{[X_1]_0} \quad \frac{d\tau_R}{dt} = \frac{k_1(T)}{(k_1(T)t+1)^2} - k_2(T)\tau_R$$

To connect the crosslink rate to the glass transition temperature one can use a simplified form of Di Marzio's relation [16]:

$$Tg(\tau_R) = Tg_\infty - cTg_\infty^2(1 - \tau_R)$$

where Tg_∞ is the glass transition for a crosslink saturation and c , a constant.

Figure 2 shows, with a few experimental values, a relation between crosslink density and glass transition temperature versus time.

Fig. 2 Crosslinking and glass transition relationship for thermal aging at 210°C

MECHANICAL APPROACH INCLUDING AGING

Since physico-chemical degradation also degrades the mechanical quality of structural composites, it is interesting to examine aging effects alongside mechanical behavior. In organic matrix composites, the predominating behavior of the resin is non-linear viscoelastic. To determine the viscoelastic behavior and degradation resulting from both aging and mechanical stresses, a numerical mechanical approach can be used. In such an approach the constitutive equations describing the behavior should include parameters linked to physical or chemical changes of the organic matrix. To represent behavior of laminates, it is suitable to use a multi-scale approach based on the determination of the ply behavior from the components behavior (fiber and matrix). The macroscopic behavior can be deduced from two consecutive transitions, first, between microscopic and mesoscopic events (the former acting at the component scale) and secondly, between mesoscopic (ply scale) and macroscopic events (laminate scale). Figure 3 shows a work program over these three scales.

To identify viscous parameters of the organic matrix, it is necessary and easy to obtain various characteristics from mechanical tests performed on the neat resin. Since this is considered a homogeneous and isotropic material, less tests are necessary to determine the viscoelastic behavior than those deduced at the ply scale (for example $[\pm 45^\circ]$ laminates). Moreover, this identification of viscous parameters is performed without any interaction with damage between fibers and matrix. This identification process is interesting since C. Petipas [17] showed some difficulties for distinguishing various damageable and non-damageable domains within a non-aged composite. Even for low loading, it was shown by microscopic observations that microcracks occur around fiber/matrix interfaces. This method also presents other advantages such as identification cost and ease of component changes. For example, if the fiber volume fraction or the fiber nature is modified, predictions can be made without restarting the whole identification process. To model the macroscopic behavior of various organic matrix composites, a numerical mechanical approach can be used over multi-scale domains. N. Carrère (paper accepted for ICCM 14) shows a schematic method for assessment of the viscoelastic behavior of polymer matrix composites.

Fig. 3 Work program including mechanics and aging

The multi-scale approach consists in determining the macroscopic behavior of any type of composite laminate from the component behavior, knowing either the macroscopic applied strain or stress. The transition between the component and ply scales is established by using Dvorak's Transformation Field Analysis (TFA) method [18]. Then the transfer between the ply and laminate scales is performed using a classical laminate theory updated for non-linear behavior. Within this approach, fiber behavior is always considered to be elastic and transverse isotropic, with perfect fiber/matrix interfaces. This model chosen to describe the matrix behavior was defined in a thermodynamic context [19]. The representative volume element, defined by a matrix ring around one fiber, is representative for a homogeneous microstructural domain. Divided by N sub-volumes, this element allows the establishment of relationships between the mesoscopic and microscopic fields using homogenization techniques. The aging effect on viscoelastic properties can be introduced inside the matrix behavior law by using an internal parameter [20]. Using an internal variable such as the glass transition T_g , the multiscale model gives a forecast of the behavior of any organic matrix composite. Figure 4 shows results of creep behavior carried out on a carbon/epoxy laminate aged under various conditions [15]. It should be noted that creep is established over short times, and that in this model only physico-chemical degradation in the volume of the material is included (surface oxidation and possible microcracking are neglected).

Fig. 4 Comparison between calculated and experimental creep data at 120°C and 3 stresses (20, 40 and 60 MPa) carried out on a $[\pm 45]_4s$ laminate made of IMS carbon fiber/ 977-2 epoxy resin and aged under various conditions (corresponding Tg).

CONCLUSION

There are now mathematical models for predicting the long-term behavior of organic matrix composites by means of natural or accelerated aging tests. Sometimes, these models include damage such as weight loss or crack density. To represent true use conditions, it would be necessary to take into account the multidisciplinary effects of all the aging factors. Subsequently, modeling would become very complex. For structural composites, it is interesting to analyze the principal aging factors such as temperature and oxidizing atmosphere in conjunction with the mechanical behavior evaluated by using a multiscale approach. Within thermo-oxidizing aging, there is competition between consolidation of the structure (post-cure effect) and degradation of the matrix (oxidation, thermolysis, cracking, phase separation, etc). For the chemical structure of the matrix, the two main effects of degradation are oxidation and thermolysis introduced by physico-chemical mechanisms. Oxidation takes place exclusively on the surface of the composite and can be modeled by kinetics related to both the oxygen diffusion and the radical decomposition and recombination processes. If the oxidation occurs as a fine layer, it represents a dominating parameter for initiating microcracks and thus plays an essential role in the properties at rupture. However, it is difficult to integrate it into a behavior law where it is necessary to define an elementary volume. For volume aging, changes of the chemical structure due to post-cure and thermolysis modify the capacity of load transfer from fibers to fibers and therefore also the viscoelastic behavior of the matrix. For aging time, evolution of the crosslink density leads to a displacement of the glass transition range. This evolution can constitute an internal variable for aging, which can be integrated into a multiscale model of the viscoelastic behavior of the matrix.

To be complete, it would be necessary to analyze the fiber/matrix interface in order to understand better the phenomenon of occurrence of microcracks leading to transverse and longitudinal cracks and delamination. Sizing and chemical treatment of fibers are major parameters for a thermal aging,

particularly for accelerated tests, because they are not expected to respond to this kind of test. We have yet to examine all the parameters given in this paper to locate those which are not suspected of chemical or mechanical action on the aging of polymers. At first glance, an analysis of this study shows that the aging of organic matrix composites is a very complex problem involving many parameters. However, analogies between behavior and structural modification of the material can be established. The examination of surfaces appears essential when one knows the importance of the health of upper plies of laminates, but this may be insufficient to show completely the decreasing resistance of materials aged under increasingly severe conditions. To take into account the damage of the whole volume of material is of obvious interest, but the analysis quickly becomes complex with the number of parameters to be combined and may not be possible with the means of investigation available. The complexity of the analysis undermines the idea of equivalence between the behavior obtained in accelerated aging tests and that acquired in the long term under true use conditions. An extrapolation of the behavior obtained over the time scales used in accelerated aging tests, for example, by a Arrhenius's law cannot be justified. To predict long-term behavior, it would be necessary to develop a model for each parameter and to include each one of them in a general mechanical model. The task is difficult but by simplifying assumptions, it seems that this proposal is starting gradually to take form.

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